

Leiden Law School
Research Data Protocol

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0. Introduction

This protocol¹ is intended to provide clear guidelines about data management for researchers at Leiden Law School. Data management includes all activities related to collecting, organizing, securely storing, using, and archiving data.

The protocol outlines the recommendations and requirements for data management, the responsibilities of different staff members, and the legal basis of the requirements. The protocol applies to all Leiden Law School employees and all persons affiliated with the Law School, including external PhD candidates and contract PhD candidates, as well as any other guests or partners who carry out research under the auspices of the University.²

The protocol includes the following subsections:

1. Research data management **guidelines**: Information for researchers at Leiden Law School, including guidelines and practical information about data management;
2. Research data management staff **responsibilities**: Outline of responsibilities of staff in relation to data management;
3. Research data management **support**: Contact information for research data management support staff and information on research data management trainings;
4. Research data management **legislation**: Detailed information about the legislation and regulations which form the basis of this protocol.

This protocol will not apply retroactively. This protocol will be reviewed and updated every two years.

¹ This protocol is based on the [Leiden University Data Management Regulations \(2021\)](#) which include requirements and recommendations for all employees, affiliates, and guests who conduct research under the sponsorship of Leiden University. Each Faculty is required to make a protocol based on this regulation tailored to the research at their Faculty. Please see the Data Management Regulations for more detailed information about Research Data Management (RDM) requirements.

² Research conducted by bachelor's and (research) master's students falls under the formal responsibility of their supervisors.

1. Research data management guidelines for researchers

This section contains information aimed at researchers. It includes requirements and recommendations related to data management.

1.1 Examples of research data covered by the protocol

Research data is any information collected or generated for the purpose of analysis, in order to generate or validate scientific claims. Examples of data targeted by this protocol can be but are not limited to:

- Survey data: collected directly by the researcher or obtained from external sources
- Audio-visual data: video or audio recordings and their transcripts
- Experimental data: data from experiments and details of experimental design
- Data acquired from third-party sources
- Observational data
- Reused data: previously collected data repurposed for new research
- Digital and non-digital data
- [Personal data](#)
- [Metadata](#)
- Research software and models: scripts, code, computational models, and software developed for research purposes

1.2 Research data that are excluded from this protocol:

This protocol does not classify documents as research data. Researchers who work exclusively with openly accessible documents (e.g., legislation, academic literature) may be [exempt from writing a data management plan \(DMP\)](#) (unless required to write one by an external funder or they are a PhD candidate). If a researcher is not required to write a DMP, they are still responsible for being clear with their research methods, data analysis, working procedures, providing references, and properly storing and backing up their research.

Examples of data that are excluded from this protocol:

- Openly accessible documents (e.g., legislation, academic literature)
- Document annotations
- Reference lists

Please contact the [Faculty data steward](#) if you have additional questions.

1.3 Leiden University Employer Copyright Regulations

According to the [Leiden University Employer Copyright Regulations \(2025\)](#), Leiden University is the rights holder for data generated by staff members, except in the following circumstances:

- Staff members whose research is supported by external funding may be subject to separate contractual agreements that govern copyright and data ownership. In such cases, these agreements take precedence over the [Leiden University Employer Copyright Regulations](#).
- Data collected by a staff member about an indigenous community: the University is not the owner but the holder of the data, and the rights of the relevant indigenous community are factored in through a mechanism, such as the [CARE Principles](#).

According to the [Leiden University Employer Copyright Regulations](#), faculties can decide to grant a non-exclusive license to a staff member so that the staff member may take a copy of the dataset with them when they leave the university. Leiden Law School recommends that all staff members are granted permission to retain a copy of a dataset unless there are unique project requirements or specific privacy or security concerns that would prevent this (e.g., criminal data that must be stored and accessed at Leiden Law School according to agreements with the research population; [collaborative projects with third parties](#) with specific agreements about data use and retention). Leiden Law School delegates the responsibility of determining this to the Heads of Departments. In the case of a disagreement about the retention of data between a staff member and their Head of Department, the [Academic Director](#) can be contacted to settle the dispute.

A copy of data collected by staff members must be retained by Leiden University for 10 years after the completion of the research to meet legal requirements. The data may be stored in a [certified repository](#) with appropriate access conditions based on the sensitivity of the data, agreements made with participants, or other agreements made during the research process. The data may also be stored locally at Leiden University.

Although Leiden University is the rights holder of data generated by staff members, Leiden University does not inherently have the right to access data or grant access to data. Access conditions are based on consent agreements with participants or other agreements made during the research process. The data may be securely stored in encrypted folders which are not accessible to the University. The [metadata](#) of the data must be accessible to Leiden University. The [metadata](#) must specify who is authorized to access the data or make decisions regarding its use, and indicate the retention period of the data or deadlines for data deletion.

1.3.1 Affiliated persons without employment contracts with the University

Seconded staff and temporary staff are governed by the same rules as employees.³

External PhD candidates, scholarship PhDs, professors by special appointment and guests are the rights holders of the data that they generate. If they work with other researchers employed by Leiden University, they must make arrangements about the jointly developed data and about the jointly developed intellectual property. Contact [Luris](#) for assistance with drafting agreements.

1.4 Data management plan (DMP)

All researchers at Leiden University are responsible for being clear with their research methods, data analysis, working procedures, providing references, and properly storing and backing up their research. Researchers must be able to provide sufficient detail about their data collection and analysis of data, including researchers who are [not required](#) to fill out a DMP.

Data management plans (DMPs) are formal documents that describe how data will be collected, reused, processed, stored, archived, licensed, published and access conditions. They help a researcher create a clear plan for managing their data from the beginning. DMPs also provide information to the researcher and other people who may need to make decisions about the data in the future. Most researchers are [required to complete a DMP](#).

³ According to section 11.6 of the [Leiden University Data Management Regulations](#) “Seconded staff and temporary staff Seconded staff and temporary staff are not employed by the University through an employment contract. The University pays the employer of the seconded staff or temporary staff for the hours worked and there is a hierarchical relationship between the seconded staff or temporary staff and the University. The rules governing intellectual property are the same as those for Staff Members.”

- A DMP must be written before the start of data collection.
- Researchers may use the template required by their funder. If they do not have a required template, they can use the [Leiden University DMP template](#).⁴ If a researcher is working with external collaborators, the template of the external collaborators may also be used.
- Researchers may contact the [Faculty data steward](#) for advice on filling out the DMP or to have it reviewed.
- A DMP should be updated when there are any significant changes to the research methodology, a change to the data storage, or a structural change to the project (e.g., new researchers added to the team).
- If a funder requires a DMP to receive a stamp of approval, the [Faculty data steward](#) can provide this.
- The DMP must be submitted to the [ethics committee](#) as part of the ethical review process.
- All PhD candidates are required to write a DMP and to upload their DMP to Converis at the end of their research.
- Researchers are required to send the final version of their DMP to the [Faculty data steward](#). The [Faculty data steward](#) is responsible for archiving the DMP.
- The DMP will be archived for 20 years after the research project has been completed.

Conditions requiring a DMP

Leiden Law School requires a DMP for most research. However, in some cases, Leiden Law School does *not* require a DMP to be written for a research project.

A DMP is required under the following conditions:

- Research that involves a human participant such as interviews, observations, surveys, and/or experiments. This also includes data which comes from publicly available sources without evident consent for (re)use (e.g., scraping data from publicly accessible social media accounts).
- Qualitative research with sources that are **not** publicly available. Examples of non-public sources could include confidential documents, internal guidelines and regulations, working documents, meeting minutes and/or materials from closed archives that are not easily accessible to the public.
- Quantitative data that is collected by the researcher or is from sources that are **not** publicly available. Examples could include datasets from governments, police agencies, or census data.
- Research funded by a funder that requires a DMP.
- All PhD candidates are required to write a DMP.

A DMP is **not** required under the following conditions:

- Doctrinal research (unless funded by an organization that requires a DMP).
- Research based on information compiled from existing sources that do not include [personal data](#) (e.g., legislation, jurisprudence, open access surveys, or journal articles) (unless funded by an organization that requires a DMP).

Please contact the [Faculty data steward](#) if you have additional questions.

1.5 Data storage

Secure storage of data is essential throughout all phases of research.

⁴ The Leiden University DMP template is accepted by most funders.

1.5.1 During data collection

- Researchers should store data in a secure location as soon as possible when collecting data.
 - The recommended storage location for data is in a project workgroup on the J:Drive. Raw personal data should be encrypted using VeraCrypt. Contact the [Faculty data steward](#) for project specific recommendations.
 - The University does not recommend storing data on external storage devices, except when necessary (e.g., fieldwork in an area without Internet). In such cases, researchers may use a password protection external hard drive. All sensitive data must be encrypted. Contact the [Faculty data steward](#) for project specific recommendations.
- Researchers should make a plan for mitigating data storage challenges before beginning research, such as being unable to access the University network in areas without Internet. Please see the [checklist for Research Data Management \(RDM\) while working abroad](#) and contact the [Faculty data steward](#) for project specific advice.
- Avoid storing data on devices that cannot be wiped out remotely in case of loss. This creates a security risk.
- Do not store or collect data on phones.

1.5.2 After data collection

It is preferred that researchers:

- Store data on the J:Drive of the research project if possible.
- The University does not recommend storing data on external storage devices, except when necessary (e.g., fieldwork in an area without Internet). In such cases, researchers may use a password protection external hard drive. All sensitive data must be encrypted. Contact the [Faculty data steward](#) for project specific recommendations.
- Encrypt sensitive and/or [personal data](#) which has not been [pseudonymized](#).
- Avoid tools or solutions that would involve data being stored outside the European Economic Area (EEA) as the data are then subjected to the local legislation which is not always compatible with the European/Dutch legislations. Ideally, the data should be stored in the Netherlands.
- Avoid storing data on devices that cannot be wiped out remotely in case of loss. This creates a security risk.
- For collaborative projects with external researchers or organizations, there should be a clear agreement regarding the storage of the data. Collaborative cloud storage solutions may be used depending on the sensitivity of the data. Please contact the [Faculty data steward](#) and [privacy officer](#).

1.5.3 Data archiving and preservation

Researchers can preserve research data by storing it in a data repository archive. Archiving data makes the data available long-term and it is necessary for the integrity of research and to comply with [regulations](#). The [minimal retention period for research data is 10 years](#). Archiving data is not the same as [publishing or sharing data](#).

If the research data is sensitive and/or in case of [personal data](#), researchers should first consult the [privacy officer](#) and/or the [data steward](#) to discuss whether the repository is a suitable and [GDPR/AVG](#) compliant storage solution, and under which conditions the data can be archived in the repository.

Researchers can use [DANS Data Stations for Social Science and Humanities](#):

- Free up to 50GB

- Guarantees permanent storage of data
- Data can be open, accessible with restrictions, or not accessible to others
- The dataset will receive a DOI which researchers can use to link directly to the data in publications, presentations and other academic outputs

Researchers may also select a different data repository. The data repository should have a [CoreTrustSeal certification](#) and it should ensure that:

- The access conditions of the data are clearly displayed
- If an embargo needs to be applied, only the description of the dataset is published
- [Metadata](#) are publicly accessible and harvestable by machines
- Provide a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI)

Sustainable file storage

- Data should be stored in formats that are durable and uncompressed or lossless, if possible. Please see DANS's list of [list of durable file formats](#).
- Stored datasets need to be well documented. This includes creating a brief description of the research project ([metadata](#)) and an overview describing information such as individual files, codebooks, and/or other relevant project information.
- Systematic file naming should be used to help easily identify data(sets). Good file names are:
 - Consistent (based on file naming conventions)
 - Distinctive (distinguish between various file versions and files with similar subjects)
 - Indicative (meaningful)
- A clear folder structure should be used to make data easily findable.
- Version management of data should be performed in order to:
 - Maintain a copy of the original (raw, unmodified) version of data
 - Identify errors that occur when working with the data

Metadata

Rich metadata of the project should be created. The most common metadata standard is [Dublin Core](#).

Project-level metadata explains the aims of the study and the methodologies used, and should provide the following information (if applicable):

- For what purpose was the dataset created?
- What does the dataset contain?
- How was the data collected?
- Who collected the data and when?
- How was the data processed?
- What possible manipulations were done to the data?
- What were the quality assurance procedures?
- How sensitive is the data?
- If/how can the data be accessed?
- Where are the data stored?

Data-level metadata provides information about the individual pieces of data in the dataset:

- Data level metadata can be embedded in the data files or written in a README file stored with the data, such as contextual or descriptive information of an interview, or names of data variables.

- For more information on data level documentation, please see the information provided by the [Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives](#) (CESSDA).

1.6 Data transport and transfer

Researchers should transfer data using the approved solutions. Please see the [University guidelines for sharing and sending files](#). The following guidelines are highly recommended:

- Contact the Faculty [privacy officer](#) if you are working with (highly) [sensitive data](#) and/or [personal data](#) before transferring data.
- Do not transfer data to persons who are not authorized to have access to the data.
- Use University-managed hardware whenever possible.
- When transporting sensitive data on physical devices, use encrypted devices and/or encrypt the data.
- [Personal data](#) which fall under the scope of the [GDPR/AVG](#) should not be transferred⁵ or transported outside the European Economic Area (EEA). Please contact the [privacy officer](#) if a data transfer outside the EEA required for research purposes.
- For things to consider when working ‘in the field’, please see the [checklist for RDM while working abroad](#).

1.7 Publishing and sharing research data

Leiden Law School encourages researchers to follow Leiden University’s recommendations for [Open Science](#) and grants researchers the [right to license and share data which they have collected](#).

Researchers may publish and share their data during or after their research:

- Researchers must have the legal right to share data (e.g., researchers cannot share datasets received from external sources without the legal right to do so).
- Researchers working with a research team or consortium must have clear agreements about data sharing.
- Participants must give [consent](#) for their data to be shared.
- Researchers working with (sensitive) [personal data](#) must consult the [privacy officer](#).

1.8 Collaboration with third parties

In the case of collaboration with third parties (e.g., with other public or private non-government entities), collaborators need to agree which party will be responsible for research data management (RDM) and create a data sharing agreement (contact the Faculty [privacy officer](#) for help). This agreement should include:

- How research data will be collected;
- How research data will be processed, accessed, used, stored during the project;
- How research data will be published;
- How research data will be archived;
- How research data will be deleted;
- Clarify issues around intellectual property rights, including copyright and terms of use.

If third parties have access to [personal data](#), researchers must contact the [privacy officer](#).

⁵ This includes using software which would transfer and/or store data on servers outside the EEA.

Co-created research with third parties

Some forms of research regard participants or informants that co-create the research methodology or published output or involve communities that assert authority to control data from or about them (see e.g., [the CARE principles of Indigenous data governance](#)). In such cases, the researcher holds the research data 'in trust' in a broader sense than the pure legal requirements and needs to carefully negotiate rights and conditions around data access, publication, and long-term preservation, as well as acknowledgement of authorship.

1.8.1 Collaboration with third parties for data processing

Researchers may work with third parties to facilitate data processing, such as transcription services. Researchers must contact the [Faculty data steward](#) prior to sharing data with external services to ensure that the services meet data protection requirements and that the data is suitable to share with external services (i.e., the data does not include highly sensitive information).

1.9 Retention period and deletion of research data

The minimal retention period for data is 10 years after the completion of the research.

Based on relevant legislation, there is no formal requirement to request the consent of researchers to delete data which have reached their minimal retention period. However, due to ethical and research heritage conservation concerns, it is recommended that the Institutes make a reasonable effort to contact the researchers involved before deleting the data. If it is a collaborative project, the Principal Investigator is the preferred contact person. If they are unavailable, the Faculty is responsible for making decisions about data deletion.

In the case of deceased researchers, it is recommended that Departments contact the relatives of the deceased (unless documents found about the research would prevent this, such as documents stating that the research can only be accessed by the researcher).

The deletion of research data is subject to formal University processes. A record of the data that has been destroyed must be created and stored indefinitely.

If the research data is published in a data repository for long-term preservation, it will, in principle, not be deleted at all.

1.10 Discussing data with departing researchers

The Faculty recommends that Departments have a discussion with researchers leaving their department, departing PhD candidates, and departing visiting or guest researchers about issues related to data and data management.

A list of suggested topics to discuss:

- Does the researcher who is leaving need/want to carry on using the research data collected during their employment at Leiden University?
 - The [Leiden University Employer Copyright Regulation](#) states that Leiden University is the rights holder to data collected by staff members. Affiliated persons without employment contracts with the university, such as professors by special appointment, external or scholarship PhD candidates retain the rights to the datasets that they collect.
 - Leiden Law School recommends that all staff members are granted permission to retain a copy of a dataset unless there are unique project requirements or specific privacy or security concerns

that would prevent this (e.g., criminal data that must be stored and accessed at Leiden Law School according to agreements with the research population; [collaborative projects with third parties](#) with specific agreements about data use and retention). Leiden Law School delegates the responsibility of data retention decisions to the principal investigator. Disputes between the departing staff member and the principal investigator can be resolved by the [Head of their Department](#). If they are unable to reach an agreement, the dispute can be resolved by an [Academic Director](#) from another department.

- A copy of the data is kept within the Department:
 - Where are the research data of the departing researcher stored? Are they stored in a workgroup on the J:Drive, stored in an external [archive](#), on a hard drive, or are there paper versions?
 - Is there project level metadata?
 - Can the research data collected by the researcher be deleted after the end of the minimal retention period or are there arrangements in place for further preservation?
 - Who can access the dataset?
 - If the data is encrypted, who retains a copy of the password?
 - Are there procedures in place for data sharing if relevant?
 - If the research data are pseudonymized, who retains access to the identification key if it has not been destroyed? If the identification key is still present, are there agreements regarding its destruction?
- Is there any additional information related to research data that has not been mentioned in the previous set of questions?

1.11 Personal data

Some researchers work with personal data. Personal data is data that could potentially be used to identify a living person.⁶

The General Data Protection Regulation/*Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming* (GDPR/AVG) applies when personal data is being processed.

- Processing refers to anything you do with personal data⁷ and requires compliance with the five principles of data processing under Article 5 of the GDPR/AVG.
- The GDPR/AVG applies if you conduct your research through Leiden University and process personal data, even if you are outside the EU/EEA.
- The GDPR/AVG does not apply when processing data from the deceased or if the data is anonymous.
 - There is a difference between anonymized data and pseudonymized data. Pseudonymized data means that a person can still be identified with one or more data points or an identification key. Anonymous data can never be traced back to the persons involved. Researchers must consult the privacy officer to confirm whether their data is anonymized or pseudonymized.

If a researcher is collecting personal data they need to fill out a [Data Protection Impact Assessment](#) (DPIA) form. GDPR/AVG obliges organizations to perform DPIAs when the processing is likely to result in a high risk. Whether this applies to your research depends on multiple factors, such as the processing of special categories of data or criminal data (see section 1.9.1) or the scale of the processing. This form helps assess

⁶ “Potentially” identify: Data that may not identify an individual on its own (e.g., gender, location, current work) may be used to identify individuals in combination with other identifying (or non-identifying) data or if that data is considered unique.

⁷ Processing includes but is not limited to the collecting, analysing, organizing, accessing, sharing, storing, altering, viewing and deleting of personal data.

the risk of collecting personal data. The DPIA will be reviewed by the [privacy officer](#) and submitted to the [ethics committee](#) during [ethics review](#).

Examples of commonly used personal data:

- Name
- Contact information (address, e-mail, phone number, social media screen names, etc.)
- Age
- Nationality
- Professions
- Video/audio recordings
- Payment/bank details
- Opinions/views on topics

1.11.1 Special categories of personal data, criminal data and data of a sensitive nature

The [GDPR/AVG](#) considers some personal data to be a higher risk or impact to an individual if processed. Therefore, processing special categories of data and criminal data is prohibited, unless one of the exceptions in the GDPR/AVG or the Dutch implementation act of the GDPR/AVG applies. In the context of scientific research, the prohibition ceases to exist when obtaining explicit consent, or when the special categories of data and/or criminal data is necessary for scientific purposes. However, the latter can only be invoked when it is (nearly) impossible to obtain explicit consent. In all cases, additional security measures need to make sure the data is securely stored and processed, such as access management, encryption, pseudonymization or anonymization.

Special categories of data are:

- Health data (including mental health)
- Racial/ethnic origin
- Political opinion/affiliation
- Religious and philosophical beliefs
- Trade union membership
- Genetic data
- Biometric data
- Sex life or sexual orientation

Criminal data includes:

- Criminal history
- Duration of (current) imprisonment

Please contact the [privacy officer](#) when intending to use special categories and/or criminal data for your research.

It is worth noting that, though not specifically mentioned in European or Dutch data protection laws, some data is considered to be more sensitive than others but does not fall under the scope of the prohibition like special categories of data and criminal data do. This is for instance the case for location data, financial data, social security numbers and electronic communications. There is an increased risk when processing data of sensitive nature. Additional security measures are therefore recommended.

1.11.2 Underage participants

Participants under the age of 16 cannot, under Dutch law, consent to the processing of their personal data. Instead, their legal representative must give their consent. Rules on the age of consent in relation to the processing of personal data may vary. Researchers who are collecting and otherwise processing data on underage participants must contact the [privacy officer](#).

1.11.3 Ethics review

The Faculty has an [ethics committee](#).

- Researchers who are working with [personal data](#) should have their project reviewed by the ethics committee.
- In certain cases, ethical review is required by external organizations, such as the Dutch Research Council (NWO).
- Research projects need to be submitted to the ethics committee before data collection starts. Review by the ethics committee cannot occur retroactively.
- Some academic journals require proof of ethical review for research to be published.

A researcher needs to submit the following documents to the [ethics committee](#):

- Application form
- Research proposal
- Data management plan (DMP)
- Informed consent form
- Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)
- Data sharing agreement (If applicable. Contact the [Luris](#) for help)

Templates of documents are available on the [website of the ethics committee](#).

1.11.4 Consent

Researchers can ask the [privacy officer](#) for guidance on developing consent forms for their research.

Collecting [personal data](#) requires a legal basis, such as consent ([GDPR/AVG](#) articles 6-7).

Consent must be:

- Freely given, specific, unambiguous and informed
- Provided in a transparent, understandable and legible manner
- Recorded in a demonstrable way
- Able to be withdrawn at any time

Consent may be obtained via a consent forms, email responses, or an audio/video recording of the participant consenting. Consent must be asked in a clear and brief way in a language that the participant understands. Consent must be given in an active way (e.g., no pre-ticked boxes or “silence equals consent”). Lastly, the researcher must be able to demonstrate that participants have consented to the processing of personal data. It is, however, not permitted to collect more data than necessary for the research goals to demonstrate the consent. For instance, if you do not need the name of participants for your research, you also do not need their names to register their consent. This is mostly the case with anonymous surveys.

Contact the [privacy officer](#) to assess whether the consent form applies with the conditions set forth in the GDPR/AVG.

1.11.5 Processing personal data without consent

It is also possible to process [personal data](#) without consent ([GDPR/AVG](#) article 6). This is for instance possible when it would be impossible to conduct the research if asking consent was required. In that case, the processing is based on the performance of a task carried out in the public interest. According to the Dutch Act on Higher Education, Dutch universities have the task to conduct scientific research.

If another processing ground than consent may apply, please contact the [privacy officer](#).

1.10.6 Reducing sensitivity of personal data

A common way to mitigate the usage of [personal data](#) is to make it more difficult or impossible to link the personal data used to a participant. This is done through pseudonymization or anonymization. The GDPR differentiates between pseudonymization and anonymization:

- Pseudonymization ([GDPR/AVG](#) article 4): Pseudonymization refers to any strategy used to make it harder to identify a participant based on a set of personal data. Pseudonymization can be done by, for example, removing direct identifiers (e.g., name, location, date of birth) and removing or summarizing other (easily) identifiable information. Pseudonymization is more common in qualitative research or research that requires personal data intact for its purpose. It is feasible for the data to be linked back to the original source, so it is not as secure as anonymization.
- Anonymization ([GDPR/AVG](#) article 11): Anonymization refers to altering the personal data in your dataset in such a way that it becomes impossible to identify the participant, either directly or indirectly, including by the researcher. This will likely mean the deletion of all identifying personal data from your dataset. Anonymization is a rigorous process and will not be possible for some types of research (e.g., interviews).

Contact the [Faculty data steward](#) or the [privacy officer](#) to discuss anonymizing and pseudonymizing data.

1.11.7 Secondary data usage

Research may use data gathered from existing sources instead of first-hand data. Such data, when combined, may reveal more about individuals than originally intended. In such cases you may need to re-evaluate the privacy aspects of the combined research data. Please consider the following steps:

- Original Consent: Determine whether the original consent obtained for each dataset covers the current intended use for your research. If not, please consult the [privacy officer](#) to determine the lawful secondary use of data. This is not necessary if the processing is not based on consent, but on the performance of a task of public interest.
- Personal profile: Assess whether combining datasets could create a more detailed personal profile. This could constitute a new processing activity under the [GDPR/AVG](#), and the data should be treated as “new” personal data.
- Original processing grounds: Ensure that the combination of data is still permissible under the original processing grounds.

1.12 Sensitive data

Sensitive data is data that requires protection from unauthorized access due to the potential risks associated with its exposure or misuse. Some examples of sensitive data are:

- [Personal data](#)

- Proprietary information
- Trade secrets
- Non-public government information
- Criminal data

When working with sensitive data, researchers should encrypt the raw data, they should only use university approved tools, and be mindful of which information they publish.

Researchers should contact the [data steward](#) and [privacy officer](#) for additional help and apply to have their research [reviewed](#) by the [ethics committee](#).

If a [data breach](#) occurs, contact the [privacy officer](#) **immediately**.

2. Responsibilities of staff

2.1 Researchers

Researchers are responsible for their own research data management (RDM), and are, in most cases, [required to complete a Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#).

Principal Investigators (PIs), who lead a team of researchers, are responsible for the RDM of their entire team, and to develop a project level DMP. They are also responsible for informing their project team members about RDM protocol, to notify all relevant parties if there are changes to the research method(s), and to update the project level DMP accordingly. PIs may delegate their responsibilities (or specific tasks) or give mandate when relevant to project team members. PIs and researchers are accountable to the Heads of Departments.

2.2 Heads of Departments

Heads of Departments are responsible for making sure that researchers are aware of the applicable rules in this Protocol (and/or specific RDM procedures). Heads of Departments are responsible for determining if [departing staff members](#) can retain a copy of a dataset. Heads of Departments are accountable to the Academic Director of the Institute.

2.3 Academic Directors

Academic Directors are accountable to the Dean. Academic Directors can settle disputes about data retention.

2.4 Faculty Board

The Faculty Board (FB) provides the means and support for the elaboration, implementation, review, and regular evaluation of Protocol. The FB is responsible for making sure that evaluations of the Protocol take place every two years or when revisions are needed to remain compliant with governing regulation or policies. The FB is responsible for the dissemination and updating of the Faculty's RDM vision and the Protocol to Heads of Departments. The FB may delegate their responsibilities (or specific tasks) or give mandate where relevant to the research portfolio holder and/or director of research and/or [data steward](#).

3. Support for researchers within the Faculty

3.1 Support staff

Data steward

The data steward advises on data management, helps with DMPs, and organizes trainings and workshops for researchers.

Data steward: Hannah DeLacey

Contact: h.s.delacey@law.leidenuniv.nl

Ethics committee

The Faculty has an [ethics committee](#) that advises researchers on ethical issues relating to their research.

Contact: ethiekendatacie@law.leidenuniv.nl

Funding advisor

The funding advisor helps researchers with research grant applications, writing and editing research proposals, and finding external funding.

Funding advisor: Jekaterina Savicka

Contact: j.savicka@law.leidenuniv.nl

Information manager

The information manager helps with information and communication technology (ICT) related questions.

Information manager: Thomas van Beek

Contact: t.m.vanbeek@law.leidenuniv.nl

Open science contact person

The open science contact person can provide advice on open science related questions.

Open science contact person: Erik van Rossenberg

Contact: e.a.van.rossenberg@law.leidenuniv.nl

Privacy officer

The privacy officer helps with questions about privacy, [GDPR/AVG](#), and information management in the context of research, education, and operations.

Contact: avg@law.leidenuniv.nl

Security officer

The security officer can help with information security questions on matters such as sharing company information or using certain software.

Security officer: Thomas van Beek

Contact: t.m.vanbeek@law.leidenuniv.nl

More information on support staff can be found via the [Department of Research](#).

3.2 Training

Trainings available for Faculty members are the following:

- [Data Management Training for Law](#)
Following this training is mandatory for employed doctoral researchers (PhD candidates and PhD fellows) and optional for external PhD researchers and other researchers.
- [How to Write a Data Management Plan](#)
Following this training is optional for all researchers.
- [The Centre for Digital Scholarship](#)
This center offers trainings on other research-related topics.

3.3 Central Support

Additional support is available to researchers:

- The [Research Support Portal](#) provides information and contact persons for questions related to all stages of research
- The [Center of Digital Scholarship](#) from the University Library offers support and trainings on RDM, open science, open access, research software and data engineering, and copyright
- The [ISSC helpdesk](#) provides resources for all ICT related questions or problems
- [Privacy Service Point](#) has information compliance with privacy law, completing a data privacy impact assessment (DPIA) and the contact information for privacy officers
- [Grant Development Office](#) provides researchers with information on applying for funding for research
- [Documentary Information and Archive Management department](#) (DIA) (*Documentaire Informatievoorziening en Archiefbeheer*) provides information related to archive management and legal requirements
- [Luris](#) is the Knowledge Exchange Office for Leiden University and Leiden University Medical Center. LURIS can help researchers with legal support related to research and to draft [contracts related to research](#), such as Confidentiality Agreements or Material Transfer Agreements.

4. Relevant legislation and guidelines

This protocol is based on the [Leiden University Data Management Regulations \(2021\)](#) which include requirements and recommendations for all employees, affiliates, and guests who conduct research under the sponsorship of Leiden University. The following legislation, agreements, and guidelines shaped the Data Management Regulations and thus also form the basis of this protocol.

Legislation

- General Data Protection Regulation or [Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming](#) applies to any research dealing with [personal data](#)
- [General Data Protection Regulation Implementation Act](#) or *Uitvoeringswet Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming* (UAVG)
- Higher Education and Scientific Research Act or [Wet op het Hoger onderwijs en Wetenschappelijk onderzoek](#) (WHW)

- Archives Act or [Archiefwet](#)

National guidelines

- [2018 Netherlands Code of conduct for Research Integrity from NWO](#)

University guidelines

- [Leiden University Data Management Regulations \(2021\)](#)
- [Leiden University Policy on privacy and information security](#)
- [Leiden University Employer Copyright Regulations \(2025\)](#)

Faculty-specific guidelines and protocols

- Ethics committees guidelines [Committee Ethics and Data](#)

Other guidelines

- FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)
- CARE principles for indigenous data governance (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics) (<https://www.gida-global.org/care> or [Operationalising the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous data futures](#))
- [TRUST](#) principles for digital repositories (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology).
- [Belmont Ethical Principles](#) (Respect for Persons, Beneficence, Justice), Belmont report, USA department of Health, Education and Welfare, 1979